

Speculation on Role of Force on the Form of the Quantum Free Particle Wavefunction $\exp(ipx)$

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We have argued in a number of previous notes that $\exp(ipx)/\sqrt{L}$, where L is an arbitrary length, maps directly to $\exp(-ipx)\exp(ipx)/L$ where $P(x)dx=dx/L$. In other words, $\exp(ipx)$ is associated with a constant momentum p , which implies a constant velocity v and hence uniform motion in space (i.e. $P(x)=1/L$ which is the uniform distribution). This, however, begs the question: Why consider $\exp(ipx)$ as a physical description of anything? $P(x)=1/L$ is a satisfactory description of uniform motion if one wishes to have a probabilistic model which ignores speed.

Here we note that a constant p (and constant rest mass m_0) cannot exist without a constant v (velocity) which implies uniform motion in x . Furthermore, this scenario implies $\text{Force}(x)=0$.

The complementary scenario is $\text{Force}(x) \neq 0$ and one may ask: Is it possible to describe this scenario in a similar manner to the constant p case? In the p constant case, x changes and $P(x)=1/L$. Hence, in the $\text{Force} \neq 0$ case, one may propose: $x = \text{constant}$ and $P(p) = \text{constant}$. In other words, the $\text{Force}(x)$ considered for a fixed x causes a change in momentum space in a uniform manner. In one case, ($\text{Force}=0$), x is a running variable and p is constant, while in the other ($\text{Force} \neq 0$), p is a running variable and x a constant.

One may ask whether there exists a single function $F(p,x)$ which describes both of these scenarios. Given that x is a running variable in one case and p in the other, p and x in $F(p,x)$ should in general be running variables. Holding one constant implies uniform motion in either x or p space. This rules out $F(p,x) = \text{constant}$. A possible solution is to have periodic motion in a complex space because $P(x)=\text{constant}$ or $P(p) = \text{constant}$ in real space. This then leads to $\exp(ipx)$ as a solution. We have noted previously that $\exp(ipx)$ uses p because it is the variable linked with force in Newtonian mechanics (second law), but this still begs the question: Why does one not have to introduce p a priori? If one considers the $\text{Force}=0$ and $\text{Force} \neq 0$ cases a priori, then it seems consistent to introduce p from the outset. We suggest that the quantum free particle wavefunction $\exp(ipx)$, which is usually thought of in terms of constant p and running x , must at the same time apply to a constant x and running p such that there is uniformity in both x and p .

Force= 0 and Force not= 0

Newton's laws focus both on the absence and presence of forces. For example, an object at rest remains at rest unless acted upon by a force according to the first law. Similarly, if no force acts on the object, it moves at a constant velocity. On the other hand, Newton's second law $dp/dt = \text{Force}(x)$ shows how p (momentum) changes with force. As a result, if one wishes to create a probabilistic theory consistent with Newtonian mechanics, it seems that a priori it should be linked to:

- (A) $\text{Force}=0$ and $\text{Force} \neq 0$
- (B) Momentum

We consider first the Force=0 case which implies a constant p (momentum) which cannot exist unless there is a constant velocity, i.e. uniform motion through x space. Given that momentum is introduced a priori as the variable in question because of its association with force, one can only state that motion is uniform, but cannot quantify it because this would involve velocity. As a result, one thinks in terms of probabilities, in particular:

$$P(x)dx = dx/L \quad ((1)) \text{ where } L \text{ is an arbitrary length.}$$

((1)) is as far as one can go with this line of reasoning for Force=0, we argue.

The next step, however, is to consider Force not=0, and we suggest that one do so in a manner analogous to the Force=0 case. We consider a priori:

$$P(p)dp = \text{constant} \quad ((2a)) \quad x = \text{constant} \quad ((2b))$$

and note that Force(x) changes p1 to p2 etc. In other words, a physical force creates uniform motion in p space at a constant x, while a constant p (Force=0) is responsible for uniform motion in x space. Force=0 and Force not=0 represent complementary situations.

We finally propose the existence of a single function F(x,p) which displays x and p as running variables, but represents the physics of ((1)) and ((2a)). F(x,p) cannot be a constant, because it is only in the case that p=constant that the physics of ((1)) applies and x=constant, that ((2a)) applies. This suggests a periodic solution in an imaginary space, we argue, which is consistent with the physics of ((1)) and ((2a)). In other words, the symmetry of the Force=0 and Force(x) not=0 cases suggests:

$$\exp(ipx) \quad ((3))$$

In order to obtain P(x)=constant or P(p)=constant, one must use $\exp(-ipx)\exp(ipx)$ which is a little unusual, but ((3)) must contain x and p as running variables. The consequences of this probabilistic approach are serious as one has a wavelength, constant/p, in x for p constant and a wavelength in momentum space constant/x for x constant. The constant/x case is very readily measurable through 2-slit experiments.

Conclusion

In conclusion, we suggest that if one wishes to create a probabilistic theory consistent with Newton's laws, one must consider both the Force=0 case (first law) and Force not=0 (second law). Furthermore, p (momentum) is the relevant variable which appears in the second law. For Force=0, p (momentum) is constant, but cannot exist unless there is a constant velocity and subsequently, uniform motion in x. If one is interested in Force=0 case and not in motion in time, then one does not know v and may write the probabilistic equation: $P(x)dx=dx/L$ where $P(x)=1/L$ is the uniform distribution.

If one wishes to make the Force(x) not=0 case analogous to the Force=0 one, one might suggest $x=\text{constant}$ and uniform motion in p space due to the Force, i.e. $P(p)dp = \text{constant } dp$. We suggest that there could be one function $F(x,p)$ describing the statistics of both the Force=0 and Force not=0 cases as these are complementary. X and p must be running variables so $F(x,p)$ cannot be a constant, but in the $x=\text{constant}$ case, it must represent a solution in keeping with $P(x)=\text{constant}$ and in the $p=\text{constant}$ case, with $P(p)=\text{constant}$. We suggest a complex periodic function $\exp(ipx)$ is a solution. We argue that p is used a priori because of Newton's second law. We also suggest that $\exp(ipx)$ emerges because of considerations of both Force=0 and Force(x) not=0 and not simply the $p =\text{constant}$ scenario which is the physical situation most often considered.